

CREATIVE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTELLECTUAL AND CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article provides information about creative psychological and pedagogical technologies for the development of intellectual and creative competence of future teachers in higher educational institutions and the possibilities of their application.*

Keywords: *higher educational institutions, intellectual, creative, technologies, psychology, pedagogical skills, pedagogical knowledge.*

КРЕАТИВНЫЕ ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНО-ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена информация о творческих психолого-педагогических технологиях развития интеллектуально-творческой компетентности будущих учителей в высших учебных заведениях и возможностях их применения.*

Ключевые слова: *высшие учебные заведения, интеллектуальный, творческий, технологии, психология, педагогическое мастерство, педагогические знания.*

INTRODUCTION

In the process of globalization of education in the world, scientific research is being carried out aimed at improving the intellectual and creative competence of future teachers, with the coordination of pedagogical and psychological mechanisms and pedagogical strategies for their development. In higher educational institutions, research institutes, large-scale work is being carried out to form the pedagogical abilities of future teachers, develop professional intellectual and creative competencies, and prepare them for pedagogical activity. In particular, ensuring high intellectual and creative competence of future teachers requires the improvement of technologies and interactive methods and forms of education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The leading factors in the intellectual and creative self-improvement of future teachers of pedagogical higher educational institutions are: the content of education, teaching methods that promote creative self-development, didactic and interpersonal cooperation of subjects in the process of mastering a profession.

The stage of the process of acquiring a pedagogical profession in a higher educational institution can be called "research", since a student-teacher will be able to master the scientific method of cognizing pedagogical reality at the primary and secondary levels of pedagogical education due to age-related features of development and experience in the process of mastering the profession. Along with an orientation towards intellectual and creative pedagogical activity, research work, the realization of creative potential, the development of creative preparation for pedagogical work, the accumulation of knowledge, skills, improvement goals are also the development of the future teacher-student and self-development.

Innovative pedagogical education in higher educational institutions is fundamentally changing the academic method of teaching both in terms of content and methodology. For example, all means of methodological support and teaching technologies are aimed at enriching professional skills, that is, the professionalism of the intellectually creative self-developing personality of a future teacher in a university setting.

In higher education, the methodological tools used for the development of intellectual and creative competence and self-improvement of the future teacher have also become popular experimentally, that is, it is expressed in intensive memorization of information using logical thinking, i.e., methods based on methods aimed at activating, and also in progressive methods of a holistic, entire orientation, connecting the activating and suggestopedic (relaxation) directions. The goal of holistic and activity methods is to introduce the student to the creative world of knowledge through fun, play and personal experience involving all channels of information perception, i.e. hearing, vision, taste and smell, sensory and inner feelings. They are aimed at the logical-figurative perception of educational and pedagogical information by both hemispheres of the brain [1, 125-140 b.].

RESULTS

All methods used for the development of creativity and self-improvement of intellectual and creative competence can be grouped according to their compatibility and effectiveness when using the main components of intellectual and creative competence in the development process, that is:

- psychological and pedagogical knowledge (didactic component);
- pedagogical skills (methodological component);
- intellectual and creative readiness (psychological component).

Thus, the trio "knowledge-skill-readiness" forms the main methodological complex of creative developmental education.

So, it is advisable to use certain groups of creative and developmental teaching methods that ensure the maximum development of the intellectual and creative competence of students who form creative psychological and pedagogical technologies.

In the context of problem-modular education, for the development of creative knowledge, one should use the methodology of "condensation of educational information" through a set of methods such as knowledge engineering, information filling, meaningful generalization, graphical representation [2, 17 b.].

The experimental language of this technology is the organization of independent work of students with folios (sheets for compressing educational information into encoded films) and media aids. The folios can reflect the content of the topic, and sometimes the whole section of the subject. For the independent solution of educational information encoded in the schemes, the future teacher-student does not have enough good knowledge of the relevant educational material, but also the ability to highlight the main and important, to find a form that distinctly and clearly at the same time figuratively reflects the content of the subject.

In particular, an enlarged composition of the content of educational material in the form of a problem module is placed on a computer monitor in the form of a sequence of symbolic images. Usually, the schematic construction of a problem module begins with the appearance of the main cognitive-graphic element, then other elements appear on the monitor in succession with it, clarifying the generalized understanding of the material being studied, and the main

connections between them will be revealed. The flowchart, through "raising from abstraction to concreteness", along with the presentation and understanding of the topic as a whole, allows you to reveal in detail the whole variety of elements of practical education. At the same time, the student, having mastered the "technology" of building a preliminary basis for finding a solution to a cognitive-graphic image, is immersed in the creation of an individual idea. Future teachers are offered flowcharts, frames, basic notes and a "set of tools" that help to find a solution to the "collected" educational information for student-teachers in pedagogical pictures: transforming models and individual diagrams into imaginary images and thereby forming the experience of understanding educational information.

Practice has shown that when studying a number of rather complex topics, most students consider this lesson boring, necessary, but sometimes impossible and unpleasant. The reason for this is that they are left alone with their memorized weaknesses when studying this curriculum, the teacher-experimenter uses the simplest version of visibility in the lecture - "frames" related to the main aspects of the topic, which are scrolled by the teacher manually, as in a cinemascope, and change sequentially - from the picture of the screen drawn on the drawing paper.

DISCUSSION

Students should be given the opportunity to independently determine the main objects and their functional relationships with other components by listening to educational material and translating it into graphic images (diagrams, models). Through this, students-teachers are prepared for a holistic view of the subject being studied, creativity and a creative approach to learning in higher education are developed.

Visual-active demonstration of didactic creativity in the presentation of educational information - activates the combination of oral and visual speech with the transformation of educational material into schemes and models, the potential of the right hemisphere, develops expressive thinking and intuition. Repeated copying of "pedagogical pictures" in the classroom and attempts to imitate the teacher in compressing a large amount of educational information in the process of independent work of the student-teacher lead the student to "sudden clarity of thought" - finding a general algorithm for constructing a graphic model of the topic, section, even the whole chapter textbook.

In the future, when working with "inexplicable" diagrams and tables, graphic models and frames, the student becomes a "student", following the path of searching for a clue to the information hidden in cognitive visualization, turning into a deep understanding of "discovery-knowledge" and the essence of things.

The final stage of knowledge engineering technology based on information compression is the transition from "solving puzzles, crossword puzzles" (A. Raikin) to compiling them, to developing your own method in independent learning, turning the author's meaning into personal meaning.

In practice, during experimental work, the transition to the level of independent creativity occurred in the process of working with educational information using computer graphics and multimedia programs.

It should be noted that it is necessary to create conditions for students-teachers to realize their real creative activity, using their own style of independent learning and the possibilities of computer graphics and design. Thus, students create text information models, process the text and present it graphically.

To stimulate the conscious and active assimilation of pedagogical theory, as well as to form scientific-theoretical, conceptual and systemic thinking, students master simple logical operations with scientific data: highlighting a concept in a text, finding its definition, describing its scope and content, showing connections with other concepts. The final work is the determination of the practical significance of the theories underlying the system of concepts.

CONCLUSIONS

As V.V. Voronov fairly said, "the student's special work with a system of scientific concepts on the topic, in particular, the creation of systematic schemes, dictionaries, after compiling scientific literature, abstracts, reports, independent scientific texts with a conditional analysis of the conceptual apparatus of the problem, have both reproducible and effective developing features. Knowledge of science and methodological skills are the result of education" [3].

So, in the process of teaching the basics of creative pedagogy and psychology, the development of creative erudition alone, even the experience of creative activity obtained as a result of self-study, is not enough to talk about the formation of intellectual and creative competence. The effective indicator of the student's creative abilities according to the technology of cognitive-graphic support of the studied educational material is the readiness and ability of schoolchildren to implement "the study of creativity in the skill of teaching creativity."

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